

Research Paper

Biological nitrogen fixation and intra- and interspecific competition in two vegetable/legume intercropping systems and their relationship to crop yield

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ABSTRACT

Legume-based intercropping systems are a beneficial alternative for soil functioning, and rhizobacterial community diversity, while can contribute to reduce external inputs. Hence, the aims of this work were to assess: (i) the biological N fixation (BNF) process of cowpea and fava bean under different intercropping patterns compared to monocultures, (ii) the relationship between biologically fixed N and the crop biomass and yields, and (iii) the possible intra- and interspecific competition processes in each intercropping pattern. We compared, for three years, the monocultures of melon and cowpea with three different melon-cowpea intercropping patterns, and the monocultures of broccoli and fava bean with three different broccoli-fava bean intercropping patterns. The different intercropping patterns were: mixed intercropping, row intercropping 1:1 (vegetable:legume), and row intercropping 2:1 (vegetable:legume). Fertilization was reduced by 30 % in the diversified plots. After three years, BNF was higher in cowpea under monoculture (16.55 kg N ha⁻¹), while fava bean showed higher BNF under intercropping row 1:1 (81.49 kg N ha⁻¹). The relative crop yield (g plant⁻¹) and plant biomass (g plant⁻¹) were sensitive indicators to assess the intra- and interspecific interactions. Cowpea showed higher relative yield under mixed intercropping (41.45 g plant⁻¹), coinciding with lower values of N derived from the air (Ndfa = 16.59 %). Fava bean showed the lowest relative yield in the mixed intercropping (195 g plant⁻¹), coinciding with the highest value of Ndfa (92.71 %). The BNF by fava bean was positively correlated with the relative broccoli yield, not observed for cowpea/melon crop. Cowpea showed no effects of inter- or intraspecific competition with similar relative crop yield and plant biomass in monocultures than intercrops. On the contrary, fava bean was more sensitive to inter- and intraspecific competition, with increased biomass and relative crop yields when plant density was low. As a consequence, for fava bean, intercropping row 1:1 and 2:1 contributed to highest relative yield (551 g plant⁻¹ and 613 g plant⁻¹, respectively) and biomass (181 g plant⁻¹ and 101 g plant⁻¹, respectively), just the patterns with lower inter- and intraspecific competition. This research provides insights about how different legumes behave differently when grown intercropped with vegetables, in terms of NBF, growth and yields: competition and facilitation processes are different when comparing fava bean and cowpea grown as intercrops. Both legume species can be recommended for intercropping systems with a reduction in fertiliser rates and no negative effect on cash crops. However, excessive interspecific competition may reduce fava bean biomass and yields, not observed with cowpea intercropped with melon.

1. Introduction

Symbiotic N₂ fixation process carried out by legumes in symbiosis with N fixing bacteria is key in agricultural systems, since it allows for the reduction in the use of synthetic N fertilizers. The long-term application of synthetic N fertilizers can result in the increase of greenhouse

gas emissions such as nitrous oxide, the inhibition of soil enzyme activities and so a detrimental effect on N and C cycles in the soil, and water pollution by N losses through runoff and leaching (Zeng et al., 2016; Yan et al., 2017). The application of synthetic N fertilizers is directly related to a high crop productivity, although only 30–50 % of N fertilizer is assimilated by the crops (Tilman et al., 2011).

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The establishment of intercropping systems based on legumes is a useful strategy for combining an increased productivity and reducing the use of synthetic N fertilizers, mainly due by the symbiotic N₂ fixation and interspecific interactions by the different species (Chai et al., 2021). In addition, this practice is accompanied by significant benefits, such as enhancing crop yields and land equivalent ratio, improving soil N and P content, enhancing C sequestration and storage or stimulation of beneficial organisms (Hassen et al., 2017; Hei et al., 2021; Cuartero et al., 2022a). In fact, the activity of rhizobia linked to legumes growth has been associated with increased soil available N and P, improving the advantages of intercropping versus monocultures (Qin et al., 2023; Benmrid et al., 2024). The mechanism regarding yield improvement mainly results from the root nodules in legume crops associated to active rhizobia, and that microbial community in the rhizosphere is stimulated by the action of the N-fixing legumes (Gianinazzi et al., 2010; Zhang et al., 2024a). The nodulation in root systems can improve the activation of insoluble nutrients, share the resources, increase soil organic matter stabilization, and enhance the N transport from legumes to neighboring plants (Wang et al., 2023, 2024a). In this regard, Marcos-Pérez et al. (2023a) observed the maintenance of soil organic C levels along with the increase of soil total N, available P and exchange K after three crop cycles when broccoli and melon were intercropped with fava bean and cowpea, respectively. In addition, the inclusion of legumes in intercropping provides other agroecological services such as improved resource use efficiency such as light, water and fertilisers (Bedoussac and Justes, 2010), improved weed control (Amossé et al., 2013), or reduced incidence of pests (Ratnadass et al., 2012).

Total biological nitrogen fixation (BNF) is influenced by soil and climatic conditions. In terms of soil, a greater abundance of mineral N in soil implies the reduction of BNF process because legumes fulfill their N requirements (Jensen et al., 2010a). However, if legume crop is developed under organic farming, N fixation is higher. This is mostly due to the fact that the external N supply from organic practices is lower, since it comes mainly from organic residues. In addition, the association of two different plant species in an intercropping system implies a competitive interaction in both crop, which results in a disproportion in soil N sources (Jensen, 1996). In this respect, Rodriguez et al. (2020) observed that intercropped cereals acquired greater proportion of soil N than the cereal monoculture owing to active BNF. In contrast to the cereal, the uptake of N derived from soil by intercropped legumes was lower than in the legume as monoculture, but this reduction was compensated by acquisition of N by BNF (Rodriguez et al., 2020). Wang et al. (2023) observed in a two-year field study, that the interspecific facilitation in the intercropping systems of soybean-maize and soybean-wheat improved crop productivity and carbon emission efficiency by reducing N input. With regards to N use efficiency, Zhang et al. (2024a) reported that maize-soybean intercropping showed 13 % lower N₂O emission rates than monocropping, attributed to 14 % and 20 % lower annually N₂O emissions in the intercropped zone than that of sole maize and soybean zones respectively. Under conditions of high soil N availability or N fertilization and increased distance between intercropped species, legumes tend to take more soil N and reduce BNF, owing to lower interspecific competition with the companion crop (Naudin et al., 2010). Hence, intercropping systems results in a certain range of interspecific competitiveness, which tend to be enhanced with an increase in the density of a particular crop, which is an important breakthrough point to increase competitive advantage (Abdul Rahman et al., 2021). As a result, further optimization of interspecific relationships in intercropping in terms of plant density is the ecological basis for improving the yield advantages of intercropping (Wang et al., 2024c).

Considering the benefits observed in previous studies related with the same intercropping systems of this study (Cuartero et al., 2022a, 2022b; Marcos-Pérez et al., 2023a, 2023b), i.e. an intercropping system between melon (*Cucumis melo* L. var *saccharinus* cv Alamo), and cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp. cv Fradel) (Crop 1), and an intercropping system between broccoli (*Brassica oleracea* L. var *italica* cv Parthenon)

and fava bean (*Vicia faba* L. cv Claro de Luna) (Crop 2), we have here studied how intercropping can affect the ability of legumes to fix atmospheric N in terms of different patterns, and how intra- and/or interspecific competition can be related to BNF and crop yield. In intercrops, fertilization rate was reduced by 30 % compared to the monoculture to promote biological N fixation and rhizodeposition. Besides the high number of publications on cereal/legume intercropping systems, there is still limited information of the effects of using legumes intercropped with vegetables. We selected melon and broccoli because they are one of the most important cash crops in the Mediterranean basin of Europe in terms of vegetable production (Nebreda et al., 2004; Rodrigo-Gómez et al. 2021). Legumes for intercropping were selected based on a similar growing cycle to the cash crop, so both species could grow simultaneously in the same field. Thus, we selected cowpea for melon (summer crop), and fava bean for broccoli (winter crop). We hypothesized that legumes grown as intercrop are able to fix more atmospheric N mainly due to the reduction in the addition of external fertilizers, and the intense interspecific competition over resources such as soil N, other nutrients and water. In addition, there should be also differences between intercropping patterns with respect to BNF process, with higher N fixation in those patterns where both species grow closer, owing to interspecific competition. Hence, this study provides new findings about biological N fixation, competition, and complementarity between two legume species and two associated vegetables, since practically all previous studies on annual intercrops have dealt with cereal/legume associations.

Thus, the objectives of this study were to assess: (i) the BNF process of cowpea and fava bean under different intercropping patterns compared to monocultures, (ii) the relationship between biologically fixed N and the crop biomass and yields, and (iii) the possible intra- and interspecific competition processes in each intercropping pattern.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study site and experimental design

The experimental design, including the different intercropping patterns and management are explained in detail in Marcos-Pérez et al. (2023a, 2023b). Briefly, the study was carried out in the Experimental Farm Tomás Ferro from the Technical University of Cartagena, La Palma, Cartagena, southeast Spain (37° 41' N 0° 57' E; Fig. 1). Climate is semiarid Mediterranean with a total annual precipitation of 290 mm and a mean annual temperature of 18 °C. Annual potential evapotranspiration surpasses 900 mm. Soil is classified as Haplic Calcisol (loamic, hypercalcic) (IUSS, 2014) with clay loam texture. The field experiment was designed as a randomized block with three replications, and each plot had 150 m². We assessed the effect of three different intercropping patterns compared to monocultures on biological nitrogen fixation and crop biomass and yield for melon/cowpea and broccoli/fava bean associations after three crop cycles. Thus, only the last year of the sequence was used to calculate the BNF. The area where this experiment was performed was set aside for the previous two years, with development of spontaneous cover crops. Previously, it was dedicated to the growth of fava bean and broccoli in rotations under organic management for five years.

2.1.1. Crop 1: melon-cowpea intercropping system

Melon and cowpea were grown for three summer seasons (2018, 2019 and 2020). Melon seedlings were planted with a density of 0.4 plants m⁻², with a spacing of 200 cm between rows and 120 cm between plants in all plots (monoculture and intercropping patterns). Cowpea seeds in the monoculture were sown with a density of 5 plants m⁻², with a spacing of 100 cm between rows and 20 cm between plants. Cowpea seeds were sown between two rows of melon in the row intercropping patterns, spacing 100 cm between melon and cowpea rows; the separation of cowpea plants within the same row was 20 cm. Thus, the

Fig. 1. Location of the experimental site: experimental Farm Tomás Ferro from Technical University of Cartagena, La Palma, Cartagena, SE Spain (source: GoogleEarth).

density of plants was 2.5 plants m^{-2} and 1.5 plants m^{-2} in the row intercropping 1:1 and 2:1, respectively. In the mixed intercropping pattern, cowpea was sown in all melon rows between two melon plants, and so in a density of 0.4 plants m^{-2} , with a spacing of 200 cm between rows and 120 cm between plants. So, density of melon was the same in the different treatments, but the density of cowpea changed.

For monocultures, plots were tilled before sowing/planting up to 1 m depth, following the traditional practice in the region. For intercropping patterns, tillage was reduced up to 15–20 cm. All crops were drip irrigated and grown under organic management. During each cycle, we applied in all plots 3100 $m^3 ha^{-1}$ of irrigation water. The amount of water applied in each treatment was controlled via volumetric water meters. The irrigation was scheduled according to climatic conditions and evapotranspiration rate (ETc). The ETc was weekly estimated according to the FAO balance as $ETc = ET_0 \times Kc$ (Allen et al., 1998); where, ET_0 corresponded to the reference evapotranspiration according to FAO Penman-Monteith (Allen et al., 1998), and Kc to the crop coefficients proposed for melon and cowpea by the ‘Servicio de Información Agraria de Murcia’ (SIAM, 2021). Melon monoculture received the equivalent of 3000 $kg ha^{-1}$ of organic fertilizer NORGAN (plan-based fertilizer with 45 % humic and fulvic acids, 3.2 % N, 7 % K_2O , Fyneco SL, Spain), cowpea monoculture received the equivalent of 1875 $kg ha^{-1}$ of NORGAN. Intercropping systems received 30 % less fertilizer quantity than the melon monoculture to verify a saving in the use of fertilizers as a result of the development of the legume. Pest/disease control in all treatments (melon and cowpea monocultures and intercropping patterns) was done using the following organic products: (i) natural pyrethrins 4 % w/v to control white flies and aphids; (ii) sulphur 80 % w/w to prevent oidium; (iii) *Bacillus thuringiensis* (50 % w/w) to control Lepidoptera caterpillars; *Bacillus amyloliquefacies* (25 % w/w) to control oidium; (iv) copper oxychloride (50 % w/w) to prevent spotted virus; (v) potassium and vegetable fatty acids to prevent aphids, and (vi) azadirachtin to prevent aphids. Harvest of melon took place on 31/07–06/08/2018, 24–31/07/2019 and 24/08/2020, while cowpea was harvested on 07/08/2018, 04–05/05/2019 and 08/09/2020. See Marcos-Pérez et al. (2023a) for more details.

2.1.2. Crop 2: broccoli-fava bean intercropping system

Broccoli and fava bean were grown for three winter seasons (2018, 2019 and 2020). Broccoli seedlings were planted with a density of 5 plants m^{-2} , with a spacing of 100 cm between rows and 20 cm between

plants in the monoculture. Fava bean seeds in the monoculture were sown with a density of 2.50 plants m^{-2} , with a spacing of 100 cm between rows and 40 cm between plants. Fava bean seeds were sown between two rows of broccoli in the row intercropping patterns, spacing 100 cm between broccoli and fava bean rows; the separation of fava bean plants within the same row was 40 cm. In the mixed intercropping pattern, fava bean was sown in all broccoli rows, with a spacing of 100 cm between rows and 40 cm between fava bean plants. So, density of broccoli and fava bean was different in the different treatments. The density in the mixed intercropping was 5 broccoli plants m^{-2} and 2.50 fava bean plants m^{-2} (like for monocultures). The density in the row 1:1 treatment was 2.50 broccoli plants m^{-2} and 1.25 fava bean plants m^{-2} . In the row 2:1 system, the density was 3.30 broccoli plants m^{-2} and 0.80 fava bean plants m^{-2} . For monocultures, plots were tilled before sowing/planting up to 1 m depth, following the traditional practice in the region. For intercropping patterns, tillage was reduced up to 15–20 cm. During each cycle, we applied in all plots 1700 $m^3 ha^{-1}$ of irrigation water. The amount of water applied in each treatment was controlled via volumetric water meters. The irrigation was scheduled according to climatic conditions and evapotranspiration rate (ETc). The ETc was weekly estimated according to the FAO balance as $ETc = ET_0 \times Kc$ (Allen et al., 1998); where, ET_0 corresponded to the reference evapotranspiration according to FAO Penman-Monteith (Allen et al., 1998), and Kc to the crop coefficients proposed for melon and cowpea by the ‘Servicio de Información Agraria de Murcia’ (SIAM, 2021). In the broccoli monoculture, 2720 $L ha^{-1}$ of NORGAN (45 % humic and fulvic acids, 3.2 % N, 7 % K_2O , Fyneco SL, Spain) and 960 $L ha^{-1}$ of ZEN (NPK 5:4:0, Fyneco SL, Spain) were applied. For the fava bean monoculture, 1760 $L ha^{-1}$ of NORGAN and 640 $L ha^{-1}$ of ZEN (Fyneco SL, Spain) were applied. In the intercropped system, the fertilization was reduced by 30 % compared to the broccoli monoculture, applying 600 $L ha^{-1}$ of NORGAN (Fyneco SL, Spain) and 400 $L ha^{-1}$ of ZEN. No pest/disease control was performed since no pest/disease incidence was detected owing to winter weather conditions. Harvest of broccoli took place on 08–09/02/2019, 29/01–13/02/2020 and 02–09/02/2021, while fava bean was harvested on 20–21/03/2019, 15–16/04/2020 and 04/03/2021. See Marcos-Pérez et al. (2023b) for more details.

2.2. Plant sampling and analysis

Plant sampling was carried out during legume flowering. Five plants

of each species were randomly and carefully uprooted in each plot to obtain unharmed roots, and were separated into roots, nodules and shoot. External rows in each plot were discarded to avoid the border effect. Roots, nodules and shoots were oven-dried at 55 °C to a stable weight, and the dry biomass was recorded as biomass. The dried shoot material was then ground using an electric mill (A11 Basic, IKA, Germany), and BNF was only determined in shoots. Crop yield and quality analyses were obtained as described in (Marcos-Pérez et al., 2023a, 2023b). Briefly, melon crop yield was determined by weighing all the fruits per plot when they were ripe and ready for consumption. With regard to cowpea yield, all the pods in each plot were harvested when the seeds were dried at the end of the crop cycle. Broccoli crop yield was determined by weighing the heads when the buds of the head were firm and tight. Fava bean crop yield was determined by continuous collection and weighting of all pods in each plot when the seeds were fresh. External rows in each plot were discarded to avoid the border effect.

The relative yield for all crops (g plant^{-1}) was calculated by dividing the crop yield (g ha^{-1}) by the density of plants (number ha^{-1}), to identify competition or facilitation processes in the different intercropping patterns, since the density of the plants is not the same in all patterns. Thus, the relative crop yield and plant biomass (g plant^{-1}) were used as indicators to assess the intra- and interspecific interactions of each legumes. The ratio crop yield to shoot biomass was also calculated. In addition, we calculated the complementary effect ratio (CE) and the aggressivity ratio (AR) (Wang et al., 2024b):

$$CE = \left[\left(\frac{Y1}{M1} + \frac{Y2}{M2} \right) - 1 \right] \times \frac{Y1 + Y2}{2} \quad (1)$$

$$AR = \left(\frac{Y1}{M1 \times P1} + \frac{Y2}{M2 \times P2} \right) \quad (2)$$

where Y1 is the yield of the vegetable (melon or broccoli) in intercrop, M1 is the yield of vegetable in monoculture, Y2 and M2 represent the corresponding values for legumes (cowpea or fava bean). P1 and P2 represent the proportion of land occupied by vegetable strips and legume strips. The CE means that land use advantage resulted from greater temporal-spatial niche differentiation due to different traits such as crop phenology and resource demand. It allows crops to realize greater relative yield due to complementary utilization of resources in time and space. When CE is positive, biodiversity effect is identified as positive effect on productivity of intercropping system. AR assess the aggressivity of one crop relative to another in intercropping, i.e., the magnitude of potential competition among the two plant species. If $A = 0$, both crops are equally competitive, if $A > 0$ then the vegetable is dominant, and if $A < 0$ then the companion legume is the dominated species (Wang et al., 2024b).

Thousand kernel weight and the protein content in grain were also recorded in both legumes. The content of N in shoots and seeds was determined using an elemental CHNS-O analyzer (EA-1108, Carlo Erba, Italy). The protein content in grain was derived from the estimated N content by the following formula (Cunniff, 1995).

$$\text{Protein content}(\%) = \text{N content}(\%) \times 6.25 \quad (3)$$

2.3. Efficiency of biological nitrogen fixation

In order to determine the efficiency of BNF in the shoot, the ^{15}N natural abundance method was used, only during the last crop cycle in both associations. The ^{15}N content of the plant samples was determined in the Servicios de apoyo á investigación (SAI) de la Universidad de Coruña, Spain, by EA-IRMS (Elemental analysis- isotope ratio mass spectrometry; FlashEA1112 - MAT253, Thermo Finnigan, USA). This method is useful when the abundance of ^{15}N in the soil is higher than in atmospheric N_2 (0.3663 %). The differences ($\delta^{15}\text{N}$) between the ^{15}N abundance in each sample and in the atmospheric N were calculated using the Eq. (2) (Bedard-Haughn et al., 2003):

$$\delta^{15}\text{N} = ((\text{Sample atom}\% \text{N} - 0.3663) / 0.3663) \times 1000 \quad (4)$$

To calculate the proportion of N derived from air (%Ndfa), it is necessary to know the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ of the N_2 -fixing legume (cowpea and fava bean) and the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ of the non-fixing reference plant (melon and broccoli) grown in the same soil as the N_2 -fixing legume (Eq. (3)) (Unkovich et al., 2008):

$$\% \text{Ndfa} = ((\delta^{15}\text{N} \text{ of reference plant} - \delta^{15}\text{N} \text{ of legume}) / (\delta^{15}\text{N} \text{ of reference plant} - \text{B})) \times 100 \quad (3)$$

As 'B' value we used -1.61 and -0.50, based on 'B' values for cowpea and fava bean shoot, respectively, taken from the literature (Unkovich et al., 2008).

To calculate the amount of biologically fixed N_2 in the harvested biomass of the legume shoot (BNF_{hd}), it is necessary to know the dry biomass (DMY) of legume in kg ha^{-1} (cowpea and fava bean), the concentration of N in the dry yield biomass in% and the % Ndfa (Eq. (4)) (Unkovich et al., 2008):

$$\text{BNF}_{\text{hd}} (\text{Kg N ha}^{-1}) = \frac{\text{DMY} \times \text{N} \times \% \text{Ndfa}}{10000} \quad (5)$$

2.4. Statistical analyses

Data were checked to ensure normal distribution using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test and ln-transformed when necessary to ensure normal distribution. The Ndfa, BNF_{hd} , relative crop yields, shoot biomass, nodule weight and crop yield per shoot biomass data were submitted to one-way ANOVA to assess the differences between cropping systems. Differences between means was developed by post-hoc Tukey's HSD at $P < 0.05$. A principal components analysis (PCA) was performed with the Ndfa, BNF_{hd} , relative legume yields, legume and vegetable shoot biomass, legume and vegetable shoot biomass and legume and vegetable yield per shoot biomass data in 2020 to study the structure of dependence and correlation established among the variables studied. Relationships between variables was performed with Pearson correlations. Two multiple linear regression analysis were carried out with the data after three years, independently for each of the legume-based intercropping systems and monocultures (cowpea and fava bean) using stepwise and backward methods. Ndfa was used as independent variable to understand if the percentage of N biologically fixed in the legumes is significantly related to relative legume yield, legume and vegetable shoot biomass, legume and vegetable yield per shoot biomass, nodule weight, physicochemical parameters in soil (bulk density, pH, electrical conductivity, total organic carbon, particulate organic carbon, total nitrogen, cation exchange capacity, exchangeable Ca, exchangeable Mg, exchangeable K, exchangeable Na, CaCO_3 , field moisture content, nitrates, ammonium, available phosphorus, available Cu, available Zn, available Fe, available Mn, available B, aggregates size distribution floating, aggregates size distribution 250_2000 μm , aggregates size distribution 100_250 μm , aggregates size distribution 53_100 μm , aggregates size distribution $< 53 \mu\text{m}$), crop quality parameters (Thousand Kernel weight and grain protein), bacterial richness (operational taxonomic units and Chao) and alpha diversity indexes (Shannon and Simpson) as dependent variables. Values for all soil properties and crop quality parameters used in the regression analysis can be consulted in Cuartero et al. (2022a, 2022b) and Marcos-Pérez et al. (2023a, 2023b). Datasets with soil and crop data are freely accessible on Zenodo (Boix-Fayos et al., 2022; Díaz-Pereira et al., 2022). Standardized coefficient (β) and partial correlation values were used for the analysis. The β coefficient is the estimated value resulting from the analysis performed on variables that have been standardized to have a variance of 1 in order to determine which of the independent variables has a greater effect on the dependent variable. Therefore, variables with larger β coefficients contribute more to the model. The partial correlation indicates the correlation between the dependent variables and one independent variable when the linear effects of the remaining variables have been

eliminated. The unstandardized coefficients (m) were used to fit the values of Ndfa versus the values calculated using the regression model. Statistical analyses were performed with the software IBM SPSS for Windows, Version 26.

3. Results

3.1. Biological N fixation and nodules biomass

Cropping system and intercropping pattern did not significantly influence Ndfa in shoot from cowpea and fava bean crops (Table 1). However, we observed that both legumes behaved differently. In this regard, cowpea showed higher values, although not significant, when this was cultivated under monoculture than intercropping systems, while, on the contrary, fava bean presented higher values under mixed intercropping (Table 1). BNF_{hb} was higher in cowpea monoculture than when intercropped, while it was higher in row intercropping 1:1 than in the other treatments for fava bean (Table 1). The Ndfa and BNF showed no significant correlation with gran protein content or kernel weight.

Cropping system and intercropping pattern did not significantly affect nodules biomass (Table 2). Cowpea and fava bean showed the highest nodule biomass in the second (2019) and third (2020) years, with no development of nodules by cowpea roots during the first crop year. Fava bean showed higher nodules biomass than cowpea, with average values for second and third years of 9.62 g and 0.23 g, respectively.

3.2. Relative crop yields, shoot biomass and complementary and competition ratios

Relative cowpea and melon yields were not significantly affected by treatments. However, cowpea showed higher relative yield under mixed intercropping (41.45 g plant⁻¹), coinciding with lower values of Ndfa (16.29 %) (Table 1). Thus, relative yield of cowpea under mixed intercropping increased by 38 %, 131 % and 113 % compared to monoculture, row 1:1 and row 2:1, respectively). Ndfa in cowpea was not significantly correlated with relative cowpea yield, but it was positively correlated with its total yield (R = 0.56; P < 0.01). BNF in cowpea was

Table 1

Estimates of N derived from biological nitrogen fixation (% Ndfa), the amount of biologically fixed N₂ in the harvested shoot biomass (BNF_{hb}), legume and vegetable relative yield (per plant), legume and vegetable shoot biomass (g per plant), legume and vegetable shoot biomass (kg per hectare) and legume and vegetable yield per shoot biomass. Values are mean ± standard error (n = 3).

Crops	Cropping system and pattern	Ndfa (%)	BNF _{hb} (kg N ha ⁻¹)	Relative legume yield (g plant ⁻¹)	Relative vegetable yield (g plant ⁻¹)	Legume shoot biomass (g plant ⁻¹)	Vegetable shoot biomass (g plant ⁻¹)	Total legume shoot biomass (kg ha ⁻¹)	Total vegetable shoot biomass (kg ha ⁻¹)	Legume yield per shoot biomass (kg ⁻¹)	Vegetable yield per shoot biomass (kg ⁻¹)
M/C	MN	33.11 ± 14.44	16.55 ± 2.46b	29.85 ± 3.45	2140 ± 61	31.37 ± 15.82	1593 ± 169	1568 ± 790	6373 ± 676	1.34 ± 0.41	1.38 ± 0.20
	1:1	16.52 ± 9.92	2.25 ± 1.60a	17.91 ± 1.47	2410 ± 375	51.93 ± 15.95	627 ± 232	1299 ± 398	2507 ± 929	0.39 ± 0.08	5.82 ± 2.96
	2:1	23.21 ± 7.40	2.97 ± 1.41a	19.46 ± 0.17	2650 ± 336	42.80 ± 6.58	833 ± 297	531 ± 206	3333 ± 1188	0.48 ± 0.08	4.52 ± 1.88
	MIX	16.59 ± 1.48	0.86 ± 0.27a	41.45 ± 8.86	2711 ± 353	44.40 ± 10.24	873 ± 76	182 ± 41	3493 ± 307	1.08 ± 0.45	3.17 ± 0.57
	F-value ^a	2.96ns	55.72***	2.64ns	0.70ns	0.44ns	4.02ns	2.02ns	4.02ns	1.13ns	2.22ns
B/F	MN	70.92 ± 7.89	46.35 ± 6.72a	435 ± 50b	334 ± 10a	68.92 ± 8.23a	346 ± 103	1723 ± 205ab	17,287 ± 5169ab	6.35 ± 0.42	1.26 ± 0.50
	1:1	75.60 ± 3.93	81.49 ± 7.28b	551 ± 21b	452 ± 18b	181.73 ± 22.01b	264 ± 70	2363 ± 286b	6601 ± 1745a	3.15 ± 0.51	2.14 ± 0.83
	2:1	74.62 ± 6.44	25.01 ± 7.54a	613 ± 92b	372 ± 36ab	101.48 ± 33.66ab	502 ± 85	812 ± 269a	16,555 ± 2822ab	7.81 ± 2.91	0.78 ± 0.14
	MIX	92.71 ± 2.81	26.14 ± 5.89a	195 ± 45a	305 ± 8a	46.38 ± 8.80a	552 ± 63	1160 ± 219a	27,608 ± 3177b	4.31 ± 0.73	0.57 ± 0.07
	F-value ^a	2.95ns	14.64***	10.24**	9.29**	7.96**	2.67ns	7.52**	6.16*	1.82ns	2.03ns

^a Significant at *P < 0.05; **P < 0.01; ***P < 0.001; ns: not significant (P > 0.05).

M/C: melon-cowpea; B/F: broccoli-fava bean; MN: monoculture; 1:1: row intercropping 1:1; 2:1: row intercropping 2:1 and MIX: mixed intercropping.

Table 2

Nodules biomass in the cowpea and fava bean roots for monoculture and intercropping patterns. Values shown are mean ± standard error (n = 3).

Legume crop	Cropping system and pattern	Nodules biomass (g)
2018 Cowpea	Monoculture	0.00 ± 0.00
	Row intercropping 1:1	0.00 ± 0.00
	Row intercropping 2:1	0.00 ± 0.00
	Mixed intercropping	0.00 ± 0.00
	F-value	0.782 ns
2019 Cowpea	Monoculture	0.12 ± 0.06a
	Row intercropping 1:1	0.48 ± 0.42a
	Row intercropping 2:1	0.22 ± 0.18a
	Mixed intercropping	0.13 ± 0.07a
	F-value	16.255***
2020 Cowpea	Monoculture	0.16 ± 0.10a
	Row intercropping 1:1	0.18 ± 0.05a
	Row intercropping 2:1	0.47 ± 0.27a
	Mixed intercropping	0.16 ± 0.08a
	F-value	5.580***
2018 Fava bean	Monoculture	0.13 ± 0.07
	Row intercropping 1:1	0.48 ± 0.48
	Row intercropping 2:1	0.22 ± 0.21
	Mixed intercropping	0.12 ± 0.06
	F-value	0.782 ns
2019 Fava bean	Monoculture	12.41 ± 1.92b
	Row intercropping 1:1	8.10 ± 0.68b
	Row intercropping 2:1	11.61 ± 2.95b
	Mixed intercropping	10.44 ± 1.61b
	F-value	16.255***
2020 Fava bean	Monoculture	10.22 ± 0.19b
	Row intercropping 1:1	10.97 ± 3.57b
	Row intercropping 2:1	8.60 ± 2.89b
	Mixed intercropping	7.07 ± 2.80b
	F-value	5.580***

^aSignificant at ***P < 0.001; ns: not significant (P > 0.05).

also strongly correlated with total cowpea yield (R = 0.98; P < 0.001). Neither Ndfa nor BNF were correlated with melon relative or total yields.

Fava bean showed the lowest relative yield in the mixed intercropping (195 g plant⁻¹), coinciding with the highest value of Ndfa (92.71 %). Thus, relative yield of fava bean under mixed intercropping

decreased by 55 %, 64 % and 68 % compared to monoculture, row 1:1 and row 2:1, respectively), following to opposite trend of cowpea. Broccoli showed higher relative yield under row intercropping 1:1 (453 g plant⁻¹) and 2:1 (372 g plant⁻¹) compared to mixed intercropping (305 g plant⁻¹) and monoculture (334 g plant⁻¹) (Table 1). For fava bean, there was a significant negative correlation between Ndfa and relative yield ($R = 0.61$; $P < 0.001$), not observed with BNF. The BNF by fava bean was positively correlated with the relative broccoli yield ($R = 0.57$; $P < 0.01$). Total crop yield for the studied crops can be consulted in Marcos-Pérez et al. (2023a, 2023b).

With regards to biomass, there was no effect of treatment on melon and cowpea crops (Table 1). Fava bean showed the highest shoot biomass per plant in row intercropping 1:1 (181.73 g plant⁻¹) and 2:1 (101.48 g plant⁻¹) compared to mixed intercropping (46.38 g plant⁻¹). Regarding total shoot biomass in fava bean, the highest values were observed under row intercropping 1:1 (2363 kg ha⁻¹). With regard to broccoli, there were no significant differences among treatments concerning the shoot biomass per plant, whereas the total shoot biomass was highest in the mixed intercropping (27,608 kg ha⁻¹), which coincided with higher values of Ndfa in the fava bean (92.71 %). Total cowpea and fava bean yields were positively correlated with their total biomass per ha ($R = 0.66$; $P < 0.01$ and $R = 0.50$; $P < 0.01$, respectively for cowpea and fava bean).

The complementary effect and aggressivity ratios were not significantly affected by diversification patterns on the melon-cowpea intercropping system (Table 3). CE was, on average, 2440, while AR was, on average, 2.22. This suggests that the biodiversity effect is positive in terms of productivity of the intercropping system. However, the magnitude of competition between the two species is highly favourable to melon. With regard to broccoli-fava bean intercropping system, CE was not significantly affected by intercropping patterns, with an average value of 2990. This also suggests the benefits of intercropping on crop productivity compared to monocultures. However, the AR showed significant differences patterns. Mix intercropping showed a positive value (0.95), suggesting that broccoli is the dominant species in the interspecific interactions. The row 1:1 patterns showed an AR value near zero, suggesting that both crops are equally competitive under this pattern. The row 2:1 pattern showed a negative value (-0.49), and so, fava bean was the dominated species in the interspecific interaction between broccoli and fava bean under this pattern.

3.3. Interaction between biological nitrogen fixation and crop and soil parameters

The PCA performed with crop parameters showed that 100 % of the total variation could be explained by the first two PCs (Fig. 2). PC1, which explained 81.17 % of variation, separated fava bean cropping (positive scores) from melon cropping (negative scores). Positive scores along PC1 were related to high N fixation, vegetable yields and legume biomass, but low vegetable biomass (Table 4). PC2, which explained

Table 3
Complementary effect (CE) and aggressivity ratio (AR) of intercropping patterns for both studied systems. Values are mean \pm standard error ($n = 3$).

Crops	Cropping system and pattern	CE	AR
M/C	1:1	2566 \pm 1606	2.11 \pm 0.39
	2:1	2520 \pm 907	2.09 \pm 0.19
	MIX	2237 \pm 1023	2.46 \pm 0.25
F-value ^a		0.21ns	2.27ns
B/F	1:1	3126 \pm 1416	0.05 \pm 0.11ab
	2:1	3220 \pm 1375	-0.49 \pm 0.35a
	MIX	2633 \pm 264	0.95 \pm 0.06b
F-value ^a		0.85ns	11.30**

^a Significant at *** $P < 0.001$; ns: not significant ($P > 0.05$).

M/C: melon-cowpea; B/F: broccoli-fava bean; MN: monoculture; 1:1: row intercropping 1:1; 2:1: row intercropping 2:1 and MIX: mixed intercropping.

18.83 % of variation, also separated fava bean cropping from cowpea cropping. Positive scores along PC2 were related to high legume yields. All treatments in cowpea cropping clustered together (Fig. 2). However, fava bean intercropped as row intercropping 1:1 separately clustered from all the other treatments, associated to higher broccoli yield and fava bean biomass, and lower broccoli biomass and legume yield.

Multiple linear regression analysis in melon-cowpea crop showed that the variation in Ndfa was negatively related to soil available P and bacterial richness, and positively related to soil particulate organic carbon ($R^2 = 0.88$, $F = 21.14$, $P < 0.01$) (Table 5). The multiple linear regression analysis in the broccoli-fava crop showed that the variation in Ndfa was negatively related to soil CaCO₃ content, the relatively fava bean yield and the soil exchangeable Ca ($R^2 = 0.73$, $F = 13.34$, $P < 0.01$) (Table 6).

4. Discussion

The intensification of agricultural practices based on monocultures and high input systems leads to environmental problems, which inevitable forces us to adapt and optimize cropping systems with lower environmental impact, such as intercropping systems based on legumes. Both intercropping systems reported here, and all their different patterns, showed benefits compared to their corresponding monocultures, as previously reported with regard to absolute crop yields and LER > 1 in all cases (see Marcos-Pérez et al. 2023a, 2023b), and the high positive values in CE (Table 3). Regardless the benefits of both intercropping systems with all patterns, findings shown in this study highlight that not all legumes have the same behaviour when used in intercropping, and this behaviour can even change depending on the companion species selected for intercropping, or the intercropping pattern adopted (Li et al., 2021; Qu et al., 2024). Our results confirm that, although LER was > 1 for both intercropping systems, two different legumes differently responded to intercropping patterns with vegetables in terms of biological N fixation and competition and complementarity processes with the crop companion. In this respect, our results are in-line with other studies where the competitiveness or complementarity between intercropped species have led to a non-proportional distribution of N sources as biologically-fixed N (Jensen et al., 2020). These differences may be related to the different physiology of each legume, different response to different companion species with different root exudates, and different weather conditions (Latati et al., 2016; Li et al., 2021; Namatsheve et al., 2024). In this line, fava bean was grown in winter and cowpea in summer because these are the periods in which these crops are more productive in the Mediterranean area.

The main difference between both legume species was that cowpea showed higher percentage of Ndfa under monoculture, and so, with high intraspecific competition (highest density of cowpea plants) and fertilisation rate. Higher BNF by cowpea was led by high cowpea relative yields, with no direct effect of BNF on melon yield. These findings are aligned with previous studies based on cowpea/cereal intercropping, that reported that cowpea can fix more N in monocultures than in intercrop, associated to higher biomass production (Kermah et al., 2018; Kombiok et al., 2007; Mogale et al., 2023). This may be explained by the fact that cowpea is more sensitive to intraspecific competition under monocultures, with high cowpea density, leading to relatively low available soil N which results in higher atmospheric fixation and accumulation (Mogale et al., 2023). Contrarily, fava bean showed the highest percentage of Ndfa under mixed intercropping, and so, when interspecific competition was higher (fava bean growing within the same row of broccoli plants), and external fertilization was low. These findings are aligned with those reported in a meta-analysis about BNF in intercrops, with overall increases in BNF and Ndfa under intercropping (Xing et al., 2023). Authors explained these results by promotion of legume N₂ fixation by specific root exudates from the companion species and transfer of N from legume roots. Chapagain and Riseman (2015) also observed that fava bean fixed higher amount of N under intercropping with wheat

Fig. 2. PCA factor scores of variations in Ndfa, BNF and other crop properties (biomass and yield) in two different intercropping associations with different patterns after three years of implementation. Colour represents legume crop (orange: cowpea crop; green: fava bean crop), and different symbols represent the cropping systems and intercropping patterns.

Table 4

Matrix of PCA obtained with Ndfa, NBF and other crop properties (biomass and yield) in two different intercropping associations with different patterns after three years of implementation (last crop cycle in 2020).

Variance explained	PC1 (81.17 %)	PC2 (18.83 %)
Vegetable yield per shoot biomass (g ⁻¹)	0.999	
Legume shoot biomass (g plant ⁻¹)	0.994	
Total legume shoot biomass (kg ha ⁻¹)	0.994	
Vegetable shoot biomass (g plants ⁻¹)	-0.991	
Total vegetable shoot biomass (kg ha ⁻¹)	-0.991	
Ndfa	0.977	
BNF _{hb}	0.900	
Legume yield per shoot biomass (g ⁻¹)		0.936
Relative legume yield (g plant ⁻¹)		0.723

than growing alone; this would be likely to the increased competition with wheat plants for soil N, promoting fava bean's greater reliance on symbiotic N₂-fixation. Thus, our initial hypothesis that legumes grown as intercrop are able to fix more atmospheric N mainly due to the reduction in the addition of external fertilizers and the intense inter-specific competition over resources has been confirmed for fava bean

Table 5

Multiple linear regression model for Ndfa in melon-cowpea monocultures and intercropping patterns after three years of implementation using soil and crop properties as independent variables.

Y	X	m	Partial correlation	β	R ²	R ² adj	F value
Ndfa	Constant (b)	4.00			0.92	0.88	21.14**
	Soil available P	-1.70	-0.94	-1.32			
	Soil particulate organic carbon	45.23	0.85	0.83			
	Bacterial richness (OTUs)	-0.12	-0.73	-0.36			

m: unstandardized coefficients; β: standardized coefficients. Significant at ***P < 0.001; **P < 0.01.

Table 6

Multiple linear regression model for Ndfa in broccoli-fava bean monocultures and intercropping patterns after three years of implementation using soil and crop properties as independent variables.

Y	X	m	Partial correlation	β	R ²	R ² adj	F value
Ndfa	Constant (b)	602.30			0.83	0.73	13.34**
	Soil CaCO ₃ content	-5.97	-0.85	-0.96			
	Relative fava bean yield	-0.05	-0.85	-0.83			
	Soil exchangeable Ca	-0.14	-0.71	-0.69			

m: unstandardized coefficients; β: standardized coefficients. Significant at ***P < 0.001; **P < 0.01.

BD: bulk density; Agsd <53: aggregates size distribution <53 μm.

intercropped with broccoli, but not for cowpea.

In relation to BNF process, the presence of nodules in cowpea roots did not take place until the second crop cycle, while the fava bean nodule biomass was very low in the first crop cycle. The lack or lower development of nodules during first crop cycle was observed in Sánchez-Navarro et al. (2019) which can be explained by the introduction of an unusual crop (cowpea) or because the legume crop has not been grown since many years ago (fava bean). For these reasons, and because rhizobia were not externally inoculated, the soil is lacking in a sufficient number of effective rhizobia or specific rhizobia strains to establish the symbiotic relationship (Unkovich et al., 2008). This situation indicates the activation of the effective N fixing bacteria which are able to carry out fixation with cowpea. In this respect, Namatsheve et al. (2021) observed that despite cowpea intercropped with maize significantly reduced cowpea nodulation, the total nodule weight was not reduced. The lower BNF in cowpea compared with fava bean can also be related to the lower weight of nodules, as previously reported (Namatsheve et al., 2024). However, previous authors have observed that competition for resources in intercrops increases nodule formation compared to monocultures (Namatsheve et al., 2024), not observed in our study.

Our results thus suggest that cowpea grows and produces better

under monoculture, with higher BNF. In fact, the positive value of AR indicates that melon is the mostly benefited crop in the association, encouraging the use of cowpea in intercropping to promote melon production while reducing external inputs. Iqbal et al. (2019) also showed the efficiency of the use of cowpea in association with cereals (sorghum and pearl millet), but reported values of AR of 13.8–14.7. These AR values are higher than in our experiment, suggesting high competition between cereals and cowpea, compared with the melon-cowpea association. Contrarily, Bezerra-Neto et al. (2023) showed AR values of 0.41–1.11 in a beet/cowpea intercropping. These results confirm the effectivity of the use of cowpea in intercropping with vegetables, which are currently understudied in comparison with the intercropping between cereals and cowpea. However, interspecific competition is not affecting both crops, melon and cowpea, in terms of relative biomass and yields, and so high relative yields are achieved in both cropping systems and intercropping patterns. This finding is highly positive because with the same quantity of water and reduced use of fertilizers, land productivity can be enhanced by simultaneous cultivation of melon and cowpea, with no negative effect on individual yields. In this line, cowpea has been previously proposed as good candidate for intercropping since it is drought tolerant and adapted to margin conditions under which other legumes may fail to grow well, with positive effect on overall land productivity (Kermah et al., 2018; Kombiok et al., 2007; Namatsheve et al., 2024).

Contrarily, fava bean was highly affected by interspecific competition by broccoli, leading to reduced relative yields under mix intercropping, which is the pattern with the highest density of both species. This competition may stimulate fava bean and associated rhizobia to increase the quantity of N derived from air (Xing et al., 2023). Correlation analysis showed that the higher the BNF, the lower the fava bean yield, but the higher the broccoli yield. This may indicate that under soil N limitation, fava bean can benefit the companion broccoli by biologically fixed N and mobilized nutrients in detriment of its own nutrition and development. Thus, broccoli growth and production are facilitated by the presence of the fava bean, which is suppressed by excessive interspecific competition. In this regard, Muoni et al. (2022) concluded in their meta-analysis, that the non-legume companion crops (mostly maize and sorghum) tended to reduce fava bean yields when grown in intercropping compared to monocultures. This has been supported in our study by higher values of AR in mix intercropping, compared to row intercropping. Jing et al. (2023) reported in a cotton/soybean field experiment, that interspecific root interaction increased the N transfer amount from soybean to the cotton roots, improving cotton biomass and yields. These authors concluded that cotton was the stronger below-ground competitor and dominant species while soybean was highly sensitive to interspecific competition, like fava bean intercropped with broccoli in our experiment. Li et al. (2014) also concluded in their review that interspecific facilitation by nutrients mobilisation by fava bean, lupine or chickpea is a common mechanism in cereal/legume intercropping systems, improving the growth and productivity of the associated crop. In this regard, Li et al. (2007) observed that fava bean facilitated N and P acquisition of the associated maize, with an increase in maize yield of 56 % in a 4-yr field intercropping experiment. However, contrarily to our experiment, Li et al. (2007) observed that fava bean also overyielded by 26 % associated with maize in comparison with monoculture, explained by different rooting depth than maize. In this respect, broccoli and fava bean have similar rooting depths of 50–70 cm, while maize roots are shallower. Thus, selection of companion species with different root depths may contribute to decrease interspecific competition with fava bean. Despite interspecific competition, fava bean also showed some intraspecific competition, since yield and biomass were higher under the intercropping pattern row 1:1 or 2:1, with high distance to broccoli plants and lower density of fava bean plants than the monoculture. In fact, AR was negative for row 2:1 intercropping, and thus suggesting that fava bean can become competitive and the dominant companion species in intercropping if interspecific and

intraspecific competition is reduced by decreasing plant densities. In this line, Neugschwandtner et al. (2022) observed higher intraspecific competition between fava bean plants during stem elongation, flowering and pod set when grown at high seeding rates. These results indicate that fava bean is sensitive to interspecific and intraspecific competition, which may decrease its yield. However, when growing in intercropping, fava bean can facilitate the development and production of the companion species, such as broccoli, or cereals (Li et al., 2007, 2014). Wang et al. (2024b) reported values of AR between 0.1 and 0.3 for the intercropping maize/fava bean, indicating low aggressivity, although maize was always the dominant crop. Nonetheless, Whang et al. (2024a) also reported that when water is a limiting factor, fava bean was the superior competitor compared to maize, thus increasing its growth and yield, because fava bean is more water-competitive. We did not observe these effects in our experiment because all systems were irrigated to fulfil cash crop demands. In addition, Zhang et al. (2024b) showed AR values of -0.22 in wheat/fava bean intercropping, indicating, as for our intercropping pattern row 2:1, that in the wheat/fava bean intercropping system, fava bean can dominate if the surface occupied by fava bean is low compared to that of wheat (six fava bean rows (2.4 m width) and 18 wheat rows (3.6 m width)). The CE between broccoli and fava bean in our study was higher than that reported by Wang et al. (2024b) for the maize-fava bean association (100–800), suggesting high complementarity between broccoli and fava bean under the experimental conditions selected in this study.

This study also provides evidence about the sensitivity in the use of the relative crop yield and plant biomass and the AR to assess the inter- and intraspecific interactions when comparing monocultures with intercropping systems with different plant densities. Land equivalent ratio (LER), CE and intercropping net effect (NE) have been successfully used to assess how intercropping affects inter- and intraspecific competition comparing different companion species (Wang et al. 2023, 2024a, 2023b). However, we found no response of CE, NE or LER to different intercropping patterns in this experiment (see also Marcos-Pérez et al. 2023a, 2023b). Thus, these ratios seem highly efficient to show the competition between crops when comparing different combinations of species, but may be not so efficient when comparing different intercropping patterns of the same associated species. The analysis of all studied ratios allows us to highlight that fava bean was highly sensitive to crop density, and so, interspecific competition, while cowpea showed the same behaviour in terms of plant density. Hence, both species can be proposed for intercropping, with positive effects on overall crop yields, but the intercropping pattern and density is important when designing intercropping systems with fava bean, supported by previous research (Neugschwandtner et al., 2022; Benmrid et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2024a, 2024b; Zhang et al., 2024b).

With regard to the ability of cowpea to biologically fix N from air, the multiple regression analyses showed that when there is low availability of soil P and low bacterial richness, the biological process for N fixation is enhanced. It has been reported that N fixation in legumes induces an increase in plant P demand to balance the N:P ratio, which can decrease P availability in poor soils (Batterman et al., 2018; Chen et al., 2022). In this line, Mogale et al. (2023) also observed higher BNF in cowpea in the treatments with low soil P concentration in a field experiment in South Africa. Low bacterial richness may be associated to decreased multifunctionality in the soil, such as organic matter mineralisation or nutrients solubilisation, stimulating nodule rhizobia to be more active at fixing air N (Sindhu et al., 2020). The soil particulate organic C is related to easily degradable organic compounds, and so rapid source of energy to help biological N fixation (Bu et al., 2024). On the other hand, for fava bean, multiple regression analysis showed that Ndfa was related to lower exchangeable Ca content. Ca is related to the protection of nitrogenase from inactivation, so roots may be uptaking high quantities of Ca to benefit nitrogenase activity (Banath et al., 1966; Wang et al., 2023), decreasing its availability in the soil.

5. Conclusions

Biological N fixation by fava bean was higher than by cowpea, but the influence of intercropping was different for each species. All intercropping systems were efficient, with high LER and CE. Cowpea showed no effects of interspecific or intraspecific competition with similar relative production and development of biomass in monocultures than intercrops. However, N fixation was enhanced under monoculture with no presence of companion species. In this line, its association with melon had no effect on melon relative yield or biomass. Thus, cowpea may be associated in intercropping systems at any pattern, with positive effects on the overall land productivity, since crop yield is not compromised in any of the associated species. On the contrary, fava bean was more sensitive to interspecific and intraspecific competition, with increased biomass development and relative crop yields when competition was decreased. As a consequence, intercropping row 1:1 and 2:1 contributed to the highest relative yield and biomass, just the patterns with the lowest interspecific and intraspecific competition. On the other hand, mixed intercropping, the pattern with the highest density of plants, led to lower fava bean yield and biomass, associated to higher biologically N fixation. In this line, the higher the BNF in the fava bean, the higher the broccoli relative yield, suggesting that fava bean is not highly competitive and companion species can take use of the available N transferred by fava bean roots. Thus, both legume species can be recommended for intercropping systems, but excessive interspecific competition may reduce fava bean biomass and yields. Nonetheless, fava bean can facilitate the development and production of the companion species, such as broccoli, with reduction in fertiliser rates. Further research is needed to assess the behaviour of other legume species and cultivars grown in intercropping with different horticultural crops in terms of BNF and inter- and intraspecific competition, to foster its use in order to decrease external inputs and increase agrobiodiversity in agroecosystems.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Virginia Sánchez-Navarro: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Mariano Marcos-Pérez:** Methodology, Investigation. **Josefina Contreras:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Raúl Zornoza:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Raul Zornoza reports financial support was provided by Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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